

KNOWLEDGE-BASED MATERIAL SELECTION

Dietmar R. Fischer

Fraunhofer-Institut für Arbeitswirtschaft
und Organisation (FhG-IAO)
GERMANY - 7000 Stuttgart 80

ABSTRACT

Designers expect more than support for the generation of drawings from the future generation of CAD systems, i.e. they need to be assisted by computer aided decision making or applications working with Artificial Intelligence (AI).

AI methods are particularly suitable for the processing of unstructured scattered knowledge for the solution of complex problems.

One of these problems is the selection of materials for construction with new materials (e.g. fibre reinforced composite materials). The number of possible combinations and configurations of these materials is too large for the user - and in particular a nonexpert user - to be able to find optimal solutions. In the course of various research programs, the IAO has developed a prototype of a knowledge-based system for material selection for design with new materials.

Data about the materials and their properties are processed and stored in a data base system. The IAO has developed a computer aided model enabling the access to material data by a comfortable graphical user interface. Selection of the optimal materials is possible through experience and expert knowledge - e. g. about production technology for fibre reinforced composite materials - recorded as rules and facts in a data base system. The expert system shell Nexpert Object provides an appropriate mechanism to store and process expert knowledge.

KEYWORDS: EXPERT SYSTEM, MATERIAL DATABASE, MATERIAL SELECTION, METHOD
DATABASE, USER INTERFACE

1 INTRODUCTION

There is an increasing demand for computer-aided design systems. This is due to the obvious advantages they offer. But designers expect more than support in the generation of drawings. Future generations of CAD systems will assist designers in the decision making process and in the subsequent applications through Artificial Intelligence (AI).

In the course of various research programs, the IAO working in the field of industrial engineering, developed a prototype of a knowledge-based system for material selection for design with new materials, whose main component is an expert system shell /2/.

The developed expert system supports the designer in selecting the optimal material, observing given technical standards of the cured component. It selects different alternatives, considering technical and economic aspects, evaluates them and offers them to the designer who makes the final decisions.

Figure 1 shows the structure of the knowledge-based system for material selection for design with new materials. It describes the relationship between the components, e. g. the knowledge base and the material data base.

FIGURE 1: Conception of the knowledge-based system for material selection for design with new materials.

The knowledge-based system developed by the IAO offers companies sufficient research potential to solve their practical problems, and is very well accepted. Such an expert system can be extended by further material groups, e. g. ceramics.

2 FUNCTION OF A KNOWLEDGE-BASED SYSTEM FOR MATERIAL SELECTION

The human-computer-dialogue takes place with the help of selection menus in the user interface developed and designed especially for this application. For instance, the designer first specifies the technical and physical loads of a component as well as the surrounding conditions of its subsequent application. Then, he accesses the knowledge-based system and specifies his demand profile. In this, the user is guided by the comfortable graphical user interface. Of course, the menus appear on the screen only on demand.

The definition of the requirements by the user is a critical discriminant for the material selection. This request profile consists of quantitative characteristics (e.g. longitudinal Young's modulus, transverse Young's modulus, in-plane shear modulus) as well as of qualitative properties (e.g. resistency against chemicals). These properties are collected in various groups.

The user interface for definition of the comparative material selection is divided into the following fields: realized parts, material pre-selection, material standards, processing methods, laminate calculation and start of the expertise. The function "comparative material selection" offers for example the possibility to compare fibre reinforced composite materials. With this function, it is also possible to link and carry out calculations to find out the properties of laminates, which can be built up out of the resin-, fibre- and prepreg data stored in the data base. With regard to the characteristics of a specific design, these calculated laminates can be compared in order to find the optimal material for a specific component with its appropriate load condition. This comparison of materials is not restricted to material classes so that, for instance, it is possible to compare laminates built out of prepregs with those made of fibres and resins.

In the mode of comparative material selection, the knowledge-based system can draw conclusions autonomously out of the requirements specified by the user in the request profile and deliver a significant material selection, considering the same aspects under which an expert would choose his material. It automatically formulates the data base inquiry out of the input in the user interface (figure 2) to get the material data needed for the selection.

Processing Method		
<p>Is a certain processing method absolutely wanted?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">yes no</p> <p>Fibre Injection Method <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Manual <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Injection Method <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Cold Pressing <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Continuous Laminating <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Wet Pressing <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Pressing of not Flowable Materials <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Profile Drawing <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Pultrusion Method <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Rotation Moulding <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Vacuum-Injection Method <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Warm Pressing <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Winding method <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>The processing method should make possible:</p> <p>Breaks <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Embedding <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Insertion of Force Inducers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Mould Removal without Part Tilting <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Production without Post-Treatment <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Undercut <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Surface Marking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Ribbing <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Beading <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Differences in Wall Thickness <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>Approximate part dimensions [mm]:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Length Width Height</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><input type="text" value="1000"/> <input type="text" value="100"/> <input type="text" value="10"/></p> <hr/> <p>Does the laminate have to be glued to other materials?</p> <p>Aluminium <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Steel <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other Metals <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Plastic <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Wood <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Will support materials be implanted in the laminate ?</p> <p>Aluminium-Honeycomb <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Nomex-Honeycomb <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Polyurethane-Foams <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Polystyrene-Foams <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<input type="button" value="Ok"/>		<input type="button" value="Quit"/>

FIGURE 2: Specification of processing conditions

The program control initiates calculation modules to locate the missing data for the material comparison. The system selects the appropriate materials and offers the results of the expertise in a prepared frame. The system offers the user the possibility to select the optimal material according to his requirements concerning material, processing methods and characteristics of the components. Using fibre reinforced materials, it also selects the suitable laminate structure for the respective design.

The special advantage of the development system is its openness and its structure of single, independent modules. Thus, the complete system is easily expandable. These modules are programs or routines written in advanced languages (C, Pascal, Prolog, etc.). When needed, they are called by the master program of the system.

After the user input, the expertise "comparative material selection" can be started. This is done by initiating the inference mechanism (i.e. the part of the system controlling the rule processing) in the expert system shell Nexpert Object.

3 KNOW-HOW DEFINITION - BASIS FOR THE SELECTION PROCESS

The knowledge-based system resorts to the knowledge and ability of experts. Problems are not only solved by mathematically provable solutions but can also be resolved with the help of vague knowledge, rules and chains of deductions. For example, experiences, i.e. diffuse expert knowledge which cannot be algorithmized, enter the knowledge-based system in form of a collection of rules and facts. All information about a special field of knowledge, achieved during expert interrogations, suitable for handling a problem out of this field of knowledge, is stored in so-called knowledge bases. These knowledge bases may at any time be expanded, changed, and compared and combined with other knowledge bases.

Figure 3 shows a section of the content of a knowledge base. Besides expert knowledge, the knowledge base also contains so-called meta knowledge. The way this meta knowledge has been defined is shown and explained by rule 8 described in figure 3. Expert knowledge, however, is presented in simple if-then-relations. For instance, if the designer intends to choose a fibre with low heat extension, then the knowledge-based system offers only carbon fibres as a solution. A calculation module starts the instructions of rule 8. If the reading of prepreg data from the data list is correct, then the module "laminate calculation for prepregs" is started. The "do"-instruction in rule 8 produces a loop across all the various laminate definitions, as previously specified in the user interface. With the execute instruction "fibre", the actual laminate is calculated. Afterwards, a utility value is calculated for the respective laminate by the execute instruction "NWA" with the help of the utility value analysis (NWA). By the subsequent reset instruction the hypothesis is put back into the initial condition, so that the data of the next prepreg can be read.

```

($RULE=R8
  ($LHS=
    (YES      (Prepreg_Read))
  )
  ($HYPO=Laminate_Calculation_Prep)
  ($RHS=
    (Do (Current_Number_Laminate+1) (Current_Number_Laminate))
    (Execute ("Fibre") ($ATOMID=Laminate_Code_Number Value;))
    (Execute ("NWA") ($STRING="Prepreg;"))
    (Reset   (Laminate_Calculation_Prep))
    (Let     (Material_Seletion2)      (TRUE))
    (Let     (Read_Prepreg)            (TRUE))
  )
)
($RULE=R9
  ($LHS=
    (No      (Next_Resin))
    (<      (Current_Number_Fibre/Number of Fibres) (0))
  )
  ($HYPO=Next_Fibre)
  ($RHS=
    (Reset   (Next_Resin))
    (Reset   (Laminate_Calculation_Microlam))
    (Reset   (Read_Resin))
    (Reset   (Resd_Fibre))
    (Let     (Material_Selection3)      (TRUE))
  )
)

```

FIGURE 3: Section of the knowledge base

4 UTILITY VALUE ANALYSIS FOR A SELECTED MATERIAL

When selecting fibre reinforced plastics, not all criteria are of equal importance for design or components. Figure 4 shows the comparative value between part and laminate requirements and processing methods in per cent. This allows to support material selection by an ordinary evaluation program. The designer, material expert or engineer can specify the importance of the individual criteria already in the request profile (e.g. importance factors with values between 1 and 10). The relation between required material characteristics and the respective utility value of a material is established with the help of evaluation functions. The evaluation functions may be linear, degressive or progressive functions. Figure 5 shows the evaluation function for the longitudinal Young's modulus of a laminate.

FIGURE 4: Comparative value between component and laminate characteristics and processing methods

With regard to the above, each material examined by the knowledge-based system has an evaluation which can be used for material selection as well as for the comparison between different materials. The result of the material selection with evaluation or nominal value of the achieved total score is shown in figure 5.

Define Function

high middle low

linear progressive degressive

Longitudinal Young's Modulus

Points

> 70000.00 130000.00 <

Unit: MPa

Quit OK

Material Requirements

General Data		Weighting in %
Fibre Content (Volume)	Define Function	25
Engineering Constants		
Longitudinal Young's Modulus	Define Function	50
Transverse Young's Modulus	Define Function	0
Ultimate Strain	X-Direction Define Function	25
	Y-Direction Define Function	0
Mechanical Parameters		
Fatigue Strength/Loading Rate	Define Function	0
Indentation Hardness	Define Function	0
Impact Strength	Define Function	0
Strength Decrease by creeping	Define Function	0
Strength Decrease as a Function of Temp.	Define Function	0
Thermal Parameters		
Thermal Expansion Coefficient	Define Function	0
Thermal Conductivity	Define Function	0
Total 100%		100
Quit		OK

FIGURE 5: Evaluation function for the material requirements (e.g. Young's Modulus)

5 DETERMINATION AND COMPARISON OF LAMINATE CHARACTERISTICS

The main advantage of a free coupling of calculation modules to the knowledge-based system is that the designer does not need to interrupt the expertise in order to determine unknown material characteristics or to include them directly into the request and selection process. This kind of coupling of external programs enables a relatively easy integration of further special modules or routines and calculation programs into the knowledge-based system, making possible a specific support for the designer. The calculation modules can be programmed in any conventional programming languages (e.g. Fortran, Pascal).

By means of optional calculation modules coupled to the system, it is possible, for instance, to carry out comparative valuations of anisotropic laminates with regard to the following criteria: laminate rigidity, heat extension coefficient, strains and stresses in an individual coat, etc. Also, references may be found regarding optimal adjusting of fibres in components and material data of fibre-resin combinations and the resulting relative evaluation.

The exact analysis of tension is reserved for the designer, e.g. by means of the finite element method. This may also be valid for further calculation methods built on an advanced theory for laminate calculation. These procedures surpass the theory of thin plates or consider special loads and element configurations, e.g. shells, stiffened plates, torsion spindle or denting behaviour of specific elements. The program "Fibre", coupled in this way, is a calculation module to determine technical characteristic values of a multi-layered composite consisting of fibre reinforced composite materials. These characteristic values are calculated during the expertise. The calculation module locates elasticity and strength values for symmetrical as well as for asymmetrical laminates, which are suitable for a comparative evaluation of the analysed material. The calculated laminates may consist of up to 38 unidirectional single layers of a fibre reinforced component material.

6 ADMINISTRATION AND STORAGE OF MATERIAL DATA

Nowadays, a larger data processing application without support of a modern and efficient data base system is nearly unthinkable. Data base systems are complex, productive software systems which may be employed in this case for administration and storage of material data, of geometrical and physical data of realized parts, developed partial solutions or other data, e.g. customized problems, boundary conditions or delivery terms. For the system presented above the data base management system Oracle was used. However, each other SQL capable data base may be employed as well, e.g. RDB by DEC (Digital Equipment Corporation). These bases offer the electronic data processing (EDP) unexperienced users comfortable user interfaces with menus, masks, mask generator and programming interfaces. This makes it possible to adapt the data base to the user's requirements and to design a more comfortable graphical user interface. Besides that, it offers text editors enabling the access to elements of the data base as well as the possibility to define various authorizations. User objects can be built up by data structures and set into relation to each other; they can be changed and evaluated (statistics); conditions for user objects (restrictions) can be predefined.

What is important is that the user is not concerned with the physical storage and data access (high efficiency demand, parallel access, fault-proneness). Concepts like data security, privacy or integrity belong to this category. The interfaces to the data base offer languages adapted to the requirements of the user like EDP knowledge, evaluation possibilities etc. (relational data base).

7 PREPARATION OF THE SUGGESTED SOLUTIONS

The presentation of the results of the comparative material selection have to show the user in a clearly arranged form the complex relations worked through during the comparative material selection. For that reason it is essential to prepare the data graphically in a suitable form. The proposed solutions should contain:

- 1 A listing of the input requirements on the material as specified by the user in the user interface at the beginning of the session. Thus the user has the possibility to check the input requirements again and to compare the proposed material with his initial requests.
- 2 Output of data sheets of found materials via graphics display and printer. The data sheets contain all characteristic values. For the output the material characteristics are clearly arranged, partially tabulated. They further contain important instructions and information as provided by the available literature. Figure 6 presents a prepreg data sheet issued on the display. If the volume of the data sheet is larger than can be shown in the display, the pages can be scrolled, i.e. the user has the possibility to regard single, distinct parts of the data sheet on request.

Database Request Result					
Number of Materials:	1	Data Sheet Number:	1	Request:	Prepregs
Abbreviation	CFK 914C/T300				
Resin	Epoxy Ciba 914C				
Fibre	Torry T300				
Resin Content [%]	30				
Fibre Content [%]	70				
Storage Life [Weeks]					
Delivery Form	100mm				
Tensile Strength [N/mm]	1250				
0 - Direction					
Tensile Strength [N/mm]	50				
90 - Direction					
Critical Shear Stress [N/mm]	84				
Longitudinal Young's Modulus [N/mm]	126000				
Transverse Young's Modulus [N/mm]	9000				
Shear Modulus	4600				
Poisson Ratio	0.300				
0 - Direction					
Poisson Ratio	0.021				
90 - Direction					
Servicing Temperature [C]	300				
Thermal Expansion Coefficient	-0.378				
0 - Direction [1/K]					
Thermal Expansion Coefficient	28				
90 - Direction [1/K]					
Specific Resistance [Ohm mm /m]	500				
Usage:	-				
Informations:	-				
Page Back		End		Page Forward	

FIGURE 6: Data sheet output of material characteristics for prepreg systems

3 A short survey with graphical representation of a "record list" of optimal materials (Figure 7).

FIGURE 7: Result of the material selection

- 4 Statistics giving a survey of the number of examined materials as well as of the amount of materials and processing methods that were not rejected because of specific obligatory requirements.
- 5 Single reports on the chosen best materials containing each criterion in tabulated form like name of the criterion, specific requirement, actual value, achieved points or importance of the criterion. Furthermore, these single reports contain the total of the achieved points of the combination of the demands on the material and on the processing methods, with a statement on the uncertainty of the evaluation.

8 SUMMARY AND EXPECTATIONS

The method described above shows a way to assist design engineers in selecting the appropriate materials for construction with fibre reinforced composite materials with help of a comfortable graphical user interface.

A special design enables this system to retrieve the optimal material from the data base system and offers it as alternative solution to the designer. The know-how recorded in the knowledge-based system permits various important complete or partial solutions for construction with fibre reinforced composite materials.

At the present stage of development, the material selection system for fibre reinforced composite materials supplies a significant secondary effect: the direct database inquiry.

The system presented above is an ideal computer-aided tool for solving complex problems arising from construction with fibre reinforced composite materials. It enables the coupling of expert knowledge from different fields in one system, thus offering the designer more capacity to concentrate on his main job.

9 REFERENCES

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BIOGRAPHY

Dietmar Fischer, born in 1959, studied Aeronautical and Aerospace Engineering at the University of Stuttgart. Since 1987 he is a researcher at the Fraunhofer-Institut für Arbeitswirtschaft und Organisation (IAO). He works in the field of technical information systems and data-base applications and is head of the group "Technical Information Systems in Design and Production Planning".

